

A REVIEW OF KUCHALA (STRYCHNOSNUX-VOMICA LINN): A POISNOUS PLANT, MEDICO- LEGAL ASPECTS AND ITS THERAPUTIC USES

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ABSTRACT

Strychnos nux vomica (Family: Loganiaceae) is a widely distributed poisonous medicinal plant. Different parts of this plant mainly seeds have been used in traditional Indian systems of medicine. Although nux vomica is extremely poisonous, still it considered to be useful for treating many diseases such as paralytic and neuralgic affections, dyspepsia, itching, urinary disorders, joint pain, dysentery, emotional disorders, epilepsy, rheumatism and insomnia. Nux vomica is extremely toxic and this is attributed to the presence of alkaloids, mainly strychnine and brucine. Therefore, more attention should also be paid to minimize its toxic potential through advanced detoxification processes without altering the therapeutic potential. Different parts of this plant especially seeds and bark possess a wide variety of indications in traditional and folklore medicines of different countries. It has diverse clinical applications in traditional Indian (e.g., Ayurveda, Unani and Homeopathy) and

Chinese medicines. Presently, nux vomica is utilized in more than 60 formulations of Indian systems of medicine of which 30 formulations are used in the disorders of vata dosha.

KEYWORDS: Strychnine, Karaskar, Kuchala.

INTRODUCTION

Botanical name – *Strychnos nux- vomica*

Family – Loganiaceae

Vernacular Name – Hindi: kuchala, English: Nux Vomica, Telugu: Mushini Ginjalu, Bengali: Kunchila, Marathi: Kajara, Gujarati: Jherkuchala, Tamil: Yetti kottai, Malayalam: Kajjila.

Synonyms – Kaka Tinduka, Karaskara, Visatinduka, Kakapiluka

Kupilu in Samhitas and Rajanaighantu – Vish Mustika is mentioned by Sushrut in the Surasadi gana. ‘karaskar’ is mentioned as a tree abundantly available near township. sodhala denoted it as risa tinduka while Bhava Mishra described it as kaktinduka or kipulu, kaiyadeca quoted a drag visamusti which may be nux vomica according to the author. Rajanighantu described five kinds of visamusti viz. vishamusti, kesamushti, sumusthi, anumustika and ksupadodi.^{[1][2][3][4]}

Botanical description - An evergreen globous tree leaf. ovate, smarved, globous, shining, obtuse, flowers. greenish white borneon terminal pubescent pedunculate, corymbose cyme fruits large about 4 cm diameter globose berries yellow when ripe.

Seeds – many about 1.25 cm diameter discoid flowering during march – April and fruits ripen during winter.

Habitat – Tropical India, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Orrisa and west Bengal ascending up to an altitude of 1350 km.^[5]

Physical properties

Rasa: katu, tikata

Guna: Laghu

Virya: vasaVipla: katu

Karma: kapha – ratahara, visaghana, grahi

There are various species of Strychnos which are distributed around the world’s tropics such as Strychnos nux – vomica, southeast Asia, especially India and Myanmar; Strychnos toxifara originated from South America, strychniys spinosa in tropical and subtropical Africa, and Strychnos potatoram found in India.

Strychnos colubrina Strychnos tibulte, Strychnos ignatia belonging to the family Loganiaceae also contains the same alkaloids.^[6]

Chemical contribution – Kipulu contain 2.3 % alkaloids in which 1.25 – 1.5 % strychnine and brucine, loganinum, sarkara, phasphali are also present.

Strychnine: strychnine is a natural alkaloid obtained from the dried seeds of plant *Strychnos nux vomica*. Strychnine is very stable and does not change in the process of pure fraction when present in a dead body and can be detected even some years after death. Strychnine is used as a Rodenticide and is highly toxic to humans as well as most domestic animals. It crystallises into colourless, in dromers, rhombic prisms, having an intensely bitter taste the human poisoning mainly occurred due to ingestion of the poison in suicidal and homicidal attempts.^[7]

Biological identification and quantification – Its biological identification is being done by various chromatographic techniques like thin layer chromatography (TLC) as chromatography and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) on performing mandelin's test strychnine presence gives aviolet colour.

Brucine (C₂₃ H₂₆ O₄) – Brucine occurs in the form of colourless, prismatic crystals with an intensely bitter taste. It is slightly soluble in cold water, but more in boiling water. Its toxic effects are only one-eighth of that of strychnine.

Biological Identification and quantification- Biological identification is being done by chromatographic (TLC) gas chromatography (GC) and high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).^{[8][9]}

Symptoms– Symptoms intervene immediately after or within 15 to 45 minutes after swallowing the poison. The symptoms include restlessness, apprehension, a heightened sense of awareness, hyper-reflexia and muscular stiffness of face and legs. It also includes respiratory distress, agitation, generalised tonic – clonic convulsions and hyperactivity. A choking sensation in the throat and stiffness of the neck and face and twitching of muscles follows. Post synaptic inhibition in many regions of brain further leads to excessive motor neuron activity and convulsions.^{[10][11]}

Sodhana Sanskara of Kuchala: The outer layer of the Kuchala seed is scraped off with a knife after it has been dried and marinated in cow's milk for 20 hours at night. After that, it is divided into little pieces and cooked for three days (approximately four hours each day) in cow milk. It is warmed with warm water after each day of boiling, dried, and then used the

next day. It is dried under cover and cooked with cow's ghee after three days so that it may be used as a medicine.

In Rasatarangini, Shodhana procedure of Kuchala is described in three methods as-

- 1. First method:** In this method, the matured and dried Kuchala seeds are taken and kept in Kanji (sour gruel) for three days and after three days these seeds are taken out from Kanji and its external Twak or skin is peeled off. Later, these seeds are dried in sun and powdered. Thus, Kuchala get purified.^[15]
- 2. Second Method:** In this type, the dried and matured seeds of Kuchala are taken and fried in a pan with ghee on low flame and fried until its outer skin becomes slight reddish (Kapisha) in colour. Once it gets the colour of red, then slowly its outer skin is removed and separated with its hot inner part removed. This method can be followed in case of rapid purification of Kuchala.^[16]
- 3. Third method:** In this method, the dried and matured Kuchala seeds are taken and tied in a Pottali. This Pottali of Kuchala seeds is placed in a Dolayantra that is filled with cow milk. This is heated for three hours and after three hours, the seeds are removed out. After the process of heating, its skin is separated and removed. With the help of iron Kharal it is powdered and by this way the Kuchala seeds are purified.
- 4. Fatal Dose** – In Adnet is 60 to 100 mg of strychnine. Two grams of powdered nux vomica, equal to one seed in weight (20 mg of strychnine) given in two parts of 1gm each have proved fatal.

Fatal period – the usual fatal period is one- or two-hour death may not occur for several hours.

Diagnosis- Strychnine poisoning has to be diagnosed from tetanus.

Strychnine poisoning	Tetanus
Onset sudden, no history of injury	Onset gradual, history of injury common
All the muscles are affected at a time	The muscles of the neck and the lower jaw are affected first (lock jaw)
During the intervene, the muscles are relaxed	During the intervals the muscles are rigid
Death takes place within a few hours; its death does not occur withing in four to six hour the probability of recovery is great.	Death may take place within a few hours and may be delayed for several days.

Treatment- It approaches to strychnine poisoning consisted of gastric lavage. Administration of activated charcoal and scribital solution, intravenous administration of midazolam continuously. pentobarbital sodium, sodium amytal, others barbituric acid should be administered immediately intravenously in does of 0.3 to 0.6 gm dissolved in 10cc of distilled water or up to five times.

Post – mortem appearances – Usually the muscles are relaxed at the time of death and after sometime extremely rigid pig or mortis sets in more rapidly and may persist for a long time the mucous membrane.

Medico – legal point: Strychnine is one of the deadliest poisons. It is rapidly absorbed from the stomach and intestine and about 20% is eliminated unchanged in the urine. About so present of strychnine take oxidised mainly by liver. In case of fatal poisoning, strychnine is found in the stomach and its contents strychnine is not destroyed for longtime in the putrefactive changes occurring in a body after death.

Pharmacological studies

Anti-cancer study

The aqueous extract of nux vomica roots was used in the study by Rao et al., and it demonstrated dose- and timedependent anti-proliferative activity against human multiple myeloma cell lines with an IC50 value of 11 mg/ml, indicating that the root extract also caused myeloma cells to undergo apoptosis in addition to the disruption of mitochondrial membrane potential and subsequent leakage of mitochondrial cytochrome.^[12]

Anti- Rheumatic Study

In 109 children who had acute rhinitis, the nux vomica 6C dilution was used. This open, multicentre clinical research showed the efficacy of the homeopathic nux vomica dilution (potency) in treating acute rhinitis. Within 7 days of the trial period, 5.50% of the children had made a considerable improvement, 14.68% had seen a complete recovery, and 79.82% had been entirely cured.^[13]

Anti Diabetic Study

Healthy albino rats of both sexes weighing 150-250g were used in the study, and diabetes was produced in the animals by giving them 110 mg/kg of alloxan intraperitoneally and fasting the rats for 24 hours beforehand. Blood samples were taken after 72 hours and tested

for blood glucose. The present investigation employed albino rats that had blood glucose levels more than 200 mg/dL and were therefore classified to have diabetes. To prevent bias, the blood samples from these rats were taken at random. Aqueous and 50% ethanolic ~ 88 ~ Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry <https://www.phytojournal.com> extracts of *S. nux-vomica* were delivered using an oral feeding needle and distilled water as the carrier fluid. Additionally, this work demonstrated that per-oral administration of the hydroalcoholic and aqueous *S. nux-vomica* seed extracts was successful in reducing.^[14]

DISCUSSION

Kuchla is an evergreen plant and the most used part of this plant are its seeds. It has a pungent smell and a bitter taste. Kuchla might be beneficial in improving appetite by increasing intestinal motility as well as gastrointestinal functions and also help prevent constipation. It might be good for diabetics due to the presence of certain constituents that help lower blood glucose levels. Kuchla also helps to manage insomnia by controlling the functions of the brain and reducing stress. It is also beneficial in managing urinary problems like burning sensation or irritation during urination due to its diuretic activity. According to Ayurveda, the administration of Kuchla is recommended only after its purification (shodhana) in different media like cow's urine (Gomutra), cow's milk (Go dugdha) or cow's ghee (Go ghrita). The final purified product is known as Sudha Kuchla. Sudha Kuchla helps to manage sexual problems like erectile dysfunction due to its Vajikarna (aphrodisiac) property. Kuchla oil can be applied on the joints to provide relief from inflammation and pain associated with rheumatism due to its anti-inflammatory property.^{[17][18]}

CONCLUSION

Kuchala represents a classical example in Ayurveda of how a highly toxic substance can be therapeutically transformed through appropriate pharmaceutical processing. In its raw form, it contains potent alkaloids such as strychnine and brucine, which are capable of producing severe toxic effects and even mortality. However, the traditional Śodhana process significantly reduces its toxicity while enhancing its therapeutic efficacy. Through systematic purification procedures described in Ayurvedic texts, the harmful properties are mitigated, rendering the drug safer for internal administration. Properly purified Kuchala has been incorporated into numerous Ayurvedic formulations and has demonstrated beneficial effects in managing neurological disorders, musculoskeletal conditions, digestive impairments, and

other chronic ailments. Thus, Shodhana not only detoxifies the drug but also potentiates its medicinal attributes, illustrating the scientific and pharmacological relevance of classical Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals in converting a poisonous substance into a life-saving therapeutic agent.

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